

TO DESIGN TASKS FOR SCHOOL PUPILS THAT RELATES WITH DIFFERENT LEARNING STYLES. (J. HARMER)

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Annotation: This article discusses language learning methods using different styles. J. Harmer's methodology is used as a basis.

Keywords: Language, method, style, school, pupil.

INTRODUCTION

As primary school teachers, you certainly know everything about children's cognitive development and first language (L1) acquisition. Though, as primary school teachers of English, what do you know about the early acquisition of a foreign language (L2)? What are, if any, the relations between the acquisitional processes of both languages? Are they governed by the same principles? Do the early stages of L1/L2 language acquisition (LA) share common features? The present module addresses these questions by providing a brief outline of the main theoretical approaches and effective methods which are being currently adopted in teaching English as a foreign language to young learners. It will primarily focus on the distinctive features of the three major factors in the learning/teaching process: The young learner, the foreign language, and the communicative context.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It is extremely important to constantly consider the different developmental stages of children at specific ages to adjust your attitudes towards your pupils as well as your teaching praxis. So, we will start with the theories which have largely investigated the close interrelation between children's *cognitive development and language acquisition*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bloom's taxonomy (Fig.1) also shows the development of cognitive stages. Each stage is characterized by specific cognitive or thinking skills which represent processes our brain use when we think and learn. Learners progress from simple information processing or concrete thinking skills, such as identifying and organizing information (LOTS or *low order thinking skills*) to more complex, abstract thinking, such as reasoning, hypothesising and evaluating (HOTS or *high order thinking skills*).

Fig.1 Bloom's Taxonomy

Such skills, if adequately oriented by teachers, can result in effective *learning* skills enabling learners to effectively respond and perform specific language tasks.

At an individual level, on the other hand, other forces seem to enhance learning, i.e. the processing and organisation of information according to learner-specific characteristics. The concept of learning styles (Fig.2) is based on a model that groups students' learning preferences into learning processes based on experiential learning through senses.

Therefore, identifying learners' learning/cognitive styles is necessary to predict what kind of instructional strategies or methods would be most effective for a given individual to perform a given learning task.

Learning Styles

<p>Visual</p> <p>* You prefer using your body, hands and sense of touch.</p>			
<p>Logical/Mathematical</p> <p>* You prefer to work alone and use self-study.</p>	<p>What is your learning style?</p>		

Fig.4 Learning styles based on the sensory-motor system

In order to feel totally involved from a cognitive as well as emotional point of view, the learner needs to be involved in a learning experience based on 'knowledge gaps' in which new information is non-discordant with his/her previous knowledge in L1. Thus, to activate the mind and enable it to modify its cognitive architecture, learning must be 'meaningful'. The main features of 'meaningful learning' are based on the following standpoints:

- learning is total, that is it involves the cognitive, affective, emotional and social sphere;
- learning is a constructive process, where new information comes to be integrated in the learner's previous knowledge;
- the quality of learning in terms of memory persistency is largely influenced by motivation which depends on internal factors such as interest, pleasure and need for learning.

The concept of 'format' dates back to 1970s theories based on the importance of common and therefore highly predictable micro-situations which form the basis of any adult-child interactions. The main assumption is that any child tends to

spontaneously communicate in a familiar context in which he would be able to recognize recurrent words and expressions linked to specific non-verbal inputs such as gestures and other visual prompts. From the language point of view the child will follow the same path already taken for the acquisition of the mother tongue from one-two words sentences (olofrasi) to vertical and more complex constructions. A strategic function in view of effective learning is played by the way activities are presented by the teacher. *Classroom management* is firstly rooted in the teacher-student relationship which has some features in common with the parent-child relationship as they both share the ability to rough-tune the language at the children’s level of language competence. Rough-tuning is the simplification of language caretakers make when talking to children in order to make their utterances comprehensible. The *comprehensible input* is also instatiated when the teacher clearly fixes precise lesson stages which start with the explanation of the lesson agenda, i.e. what they are going to do during the lesson, end with a short summary of what they have learned and predict the content of the next lesson. The general method/approach the teacher will adopt will be also signalled by the different arrangements of chairs and desks.

Fig.6 (from J. Harmer, How to teach English, 2nd ed., p.42)

["The meaning of the words of a given language, and how they can be used in combination, depends on the perception and categorization of the real world around us" (Nick C. Ellis p.65in Handbook of SLA)]

TEACHER EDUCATION TASKS

TASK 1

Consider the materials and activities in the Appendixes 1, 2, 3 and 4:

- 1) Number the tasks and define them according to teaching procedures (e.g warm-up, presentation, practice, production).
- 2) Indicate the learning outcomes of each task by referring to Bloom's taxonomy: which cognitive skills are involved?
- 3) What task could be used for extension? Why?
- 4) Indicate in the table below which communicative functions, speech acts and corresponding exponents may be taught by using the text "Healthy Food."

Function	Speech act	Exponents
Personal		
Interpersonal		
Directive		
Referential		
Imaginative		

APPENDIX No. _____

Step: _____

Search for the origin of your favourite foods, then report to the class.

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